

Analysis of Out of Specification Causes in Indian Pharma

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Abstract

Objectives: This research explores the underlying reasons behind Out of Specification (OOS) findings in Indian pharmaceutical companies by reviewing the responses gathered through a planned questionnaire.

Methodology: The responses summarized in Tables 1a, 1b, and 1c revealed recurring challenges such as inconsistent manufacturing practices, inadequate process control, insufficient analytical verification, and limited workforce expertise. A mixed-method approach was used, combining qualitative feedback with descriptive analysis. Data were collected using a Google Forms questionnaire shared with professionals from manufacturing and quality functions. All responses were organized and examined through a comparative thematic analysis to identify trends and contributing causes.

Results: Findings showed that pressure to meet production timelines sometimes resulted in shortcuts, leading to product quality failures. Several respondents acknowledged weaknesses in investigation practices, including incomplete assessments and failure to appropriately justify or record failing results. Limited training and unclear procedural guidance were also identified as significant barriers to effective OOS management.

Conclusion: The study highlights the need for structured procedures, preventive controls, trained personnel, and strong documentation to ensure consistent compliance. A systematic approach supported by continuous monitoring and accountability may significantly reduce OOS occurrences and enhance regulatory alignment.

Keyword

Corrective and Preventive Actions, Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP), Out of Specification, Quality Control, Standard Operating Procedure, United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA)

INTRODUCTION

In pharmaceutical manufacturing, the assurance of product quality, regulatory compliance, and patient safety represents a foundational requirement rather than a procedural expectation (Kumar & Gupta, 2015; Jain & Jain, 2020). Among multiple quality oversight mechanisms, the regulatory examination of Out-of-Specification (OOS) analytical results remains a critical focus area during inspections (Swartz & Krull, 2004; Ravi et al., 2013). An OOS result refers to analytical observations that fall outside established acceptance limits defined by compendial standards, submissions, or validated internal specifications (United States Pharmacopeia, 2020; FDA, 2022). Such findings may indicate potential variability in analytical performance or process consistency and therefore raise concerns regarding product reliability and regulatory compliance (Hoinowski et al., 2002; Rathore et al., 2023).

To address such cases, the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) has issued

formal guidance outlining principles and expectations for documenting and evaluating OOS test outcomes (FDA, 2022; Indian FDA Guidance, 2022). This document emphasizes that every OOS observation whether preliminary or confirmed must undergo a scientifically justified, traceable, and comprehensive investigation (McDowall, 2020; Patel, 2012). The USFDA proposes a structured two-tier model for handling OOS events (Ravi et al., 2013).

The first phase involves a targeted laboratory assessment to determine whether analytical error, procedural deviations, Instrument malfunction or operator-related issues contributed to the result (Hoinowski et al., 2002; Pazhayatil et al., 2019). During this step, factors such as sample traceability, analyst qualification, equipment calibration status, raw-data integrity, and compliance with validated analytical methodology must be verified (Unger, 2014; Poska & Graham, 2009). If laboratory-based factors are confirmed, a justified retest may be performed; however, when no analytical cause is identified, a second phase investigation is required (FDA, 2023).

Phase II involves a comprehensive review of the manufacturing process to identify potential root causes linked to raw material variation, environmental control, batch record documentation, equipment maintenance, in-process control data, and operator training (Tripathy et al., 2017; Deshpande et al., 2020). When a cause is identified, corrective and preventive actions (CAPA) must be implemented and recorded (Jain & Jain, 2017). If no assignable cause is confirmed, the original OOS result remains valid and the associated batch must be dispositioned based on regulatory compliance expectations (Patel et al., 2023; Shah, 2020).

Regulatory bodies caution against practices such as unjustified retesting, selective result reporting, or data manipulation, which are considered serious data integrity violations (Frank, 1991; Winchell, 2011). All data including failing results must remain part of the official record and cannot be excluded from regulatory or release decision making (Poska & Graham, 2009; McDowall, 2020).

In India, regulatory frameworks under the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) and Schedule M require structured OOS investigation systems aligned with data integrity expectations (Gowtham et al., 2011; Kolekar & Bhagwat, 2021). Many manufacturers adopt international frameworks such as the World Health Organization Technical Report Series (WHO TRS) to harmonize quality systems with global inspection standards (World Health Organization, 2017, 2018, 2020).

OOS findings remain among the most common causes of USFDA Form 483 observations and warning letters issued to Indian manufacturers (Patel et al., 2022; Shashikant et al., 2018). Frequent deficiencies include inadequate root-cause justification, incomplete documentation, deviation from SOPs, or intentional testing into compliance (Neves et al., 2020; Unger, 2014).

In conclusion, a disciplined, transparent, and scientifically justified approach to OOS investigations is essential for ensuring regulatory compliance, maintaining robust pharmaceutical quality systems, and protecting patient safety (Kamal et al., 2024; Deshpande et al., 2020).

Regulatory Guidelines

Various global health authorities have established structured regulatory expectations for managing Out-of-Specification (OOS) results during pharmaceutical testing and manufacturing (FDA, 2022; World Health Organization, 2020). Among these, one of the most widely referenced frameworks is issued by the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA), which initially published its foundational document in 2006 titled Investigating Out-of-Specification (OOS) Test Results for Pharmaceutical Production and later expanded interpretive clarifications in subsequent years (Indian FDA Guidance, 2022;

Unger, 2014). This guidance details a two-stage investigation model beginning with analytical-level verification and extending into a manufacturing-level evaluation when no laboratory error is demonstrated. The document further emphasizes traceable documentation, justification for repeat testing, and prohibits any form of selective reporting or data manipulation (McDowall, 2020; Frank, 1991).

Within the European Union (EU), expectations surrounding OOS handling are embedded within Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) requirements described in EudraLex Volume 4, particularly within Chapter 1 on pharmaceutical quality systems and Chapter 6 on quality control (European Commission, 2020). These sections mandate comprehensive documentation, scientific justification of deviations, and implementation of corrective and preventive measures to prevent recurrence (Chatterjee et al., 2021; Deshpande et al., 2020).

In India, regulatory expectations are outlined under Schedule M of the Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940, overseen by the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO). Although CDSCO does not publish a separate OOS-specific guideline, regulated manufacturers are expected to align their procedures with WHO and USFDA expectations and maintain predefined written procedures for assessing unexpected analytical results (Gowtham et al., 2011; Patel et al., 2022). In the United Kingdom, the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) offers a more detailed interpretation with a dedicated OOS guidance document that provides investigation flowcharts, distinctions between atypical and true OOS results, and expectations for re-analysis (Poska & Graham, 2009; Pazhayatil et al., 2019).

While the Pharmaceutical Inspection Co-operation Scheme (PIC/S) has not released an independent guideline solely focused on OOS management, its GMP Guide (PE 009-17) incorporates mandatory expectations for handling abnormal or nonconforming results (EMA, 2017; World Health Organization, 2018). This framework requires immediate investigation, appropriate risk-based evaluation, and alignment across relevant functional groups prior to a final batch disposition decision. Figure 1 illustrates the comparative regulatory landscape and summarizes expectations from major health agencies for OOS handling.

Figure 1: Major OOS Regulatory Guidelines

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the author reviewed multiple credible information sources, including peer-reviewed research articles, USFDA Form 483 observations, and official warning letters issued to pharmaceutical manufacturing organizations (Rathore et al., 2023). Key regulatory documents related to Out-of-Specification (OOS) handling particularly those from the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) and the World Health Organization Technical Report Series (WHO TRS) were also consulted to ensure alignment with globally accepted compliance expectations (World Health Organization, 2017; FDA, 2022). To strengthen the literature review, additional online regulatory resources and recently published scientific findings were examined (McDowall, 2020; Neves et al., 2020).

To incorporate practical perspectives from the pharmaceutical sector, the author developed a structured questionnaire as part of the primary research design (Jain & Jain, 2020). The questionnaire was reviewed and approved by both the research guide and co-guide prior to circulation. It was then converted into a digital format using Google Forms and distributed to industry professionals working in pharmaceutical quality, regulatory affairs, and manufacturing functions (Patel et al., 2022). Figure 2 provides an overview of the methodological workflow, from study initiation to data collection and analysis. Information regarding questionnaire distribution and response patterns is summarized in Tables 1a, 1b, and 1c.

Figure 2: Research Methodology for OOS

The central objective of this study is to identify common causes of OOS findings cited in USFDA Form 483 inspection observations and regulatory correspondence issued to Indian pharmaceutical establishments (Unger, 2014; Patel, 2012). The scope of the research is limited to organizations engaged in drug manufacturing and does not include sectors such as medical devices, biotechnological products, or food-related industries. Tables 1a, 1b, and 1c list the pharmaceutical companies that participated in the survey along with their corresponding responses. A total of eleven (09) organizations contributed feedback for this research study.

Company Name	What are observations on OOS investigation by USFDA in your company?	What are the main reasons for inadequate investigation of OOS results?	Why do OOS results occur frequently?	Why are quick fixes often chosen over thorough OOS investigations?	Why are documentation practices often inadequate in OOS investigations
Company A Mumbai, India.	Original failing results invalidated without proper	Inadequate investigation Procedures	Inconsistent manufacturing processes	Due to lack of investigation skills	Insufficient training on documentation

	investigation / justification / rationale				
Company B Andhra Pradesh, India.	The investigation was deficient as root cause was not identified	Lack of experienced personnel, Inadequate documentation and record-keeping, Inadequate investigation Procedures	Inconsistent manufacturing processes, Inadequate Analytical Pre Check	Due to lack of investigation skills, Due to perceived non-critical nature of the issue	Insufficient training on documentation
Company C Boisar, Maharashtra, India.	Original failing results invalidated without proper investigation / justification / rationale	Lack of experienced personnel	Inconsistent manufacturing processes	Due to lack of investigation skills	Insufficient training on documentation

Table 1a – Company Name and Feedback

Company Name	What are observations on OOS investigation by USFDA in your company?	What are the main reasons for inadequate investigation of OOS results?	Why do OOS results occur frequently?	Why are quick fixes often chosen over thorough OOS investigations?	Why are documentation practices often inadequate in OOS investigations
Company D Boisar, Maharashtra, India.	All OOS were not logged	Inadequate investigation Procedures	Inadequate process controls	Due to lack of investigation skills	Lack of standardized procedures
Company E Indore, India.	All OOS were not logged	Inadequate documentation and record-keeping	Inconsistent manufacturing processes	To meet production targets	Time constraints,
Company F India	All OOS were not logged	Insufficient training on documentation	Inconsistent manufacturing processes	To meet production targets	Insufficient training on documentati
Company G Mumbai, India.	The investigation was deficient as root cause was not identified, Original failing results invalidated without	Lack of experienced personnel, Pressure to resume production quickly,	Inconsistent manufacturing processes, Inadequate	To meet production targets, Due to perceived	Lack of standardized procedures, Insufficient

	proper investigation / justification / rationale, Repeat testing was carried out without proper justification and approval of QA, CAPA was not effective as the same OOS results were obtained after taking CAPA	Inadequate documentation and record-keeping	process controls	non-critical nature of the issue	training on documentation
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Table 1b – Company Name and Feedback

Company Name	What are observations on OOS investigation by USFDA in your company?	What are the main reasons for inadequate investigation of OOS results?	Why do OOS results occur frequently?	Why are quick fixes often chosen over thorough OOS investigations?	Why are documentation practices often inadequate in OOS investigations
Company H, Maharashtra, India	The investigation was deficient as root cause was not identified	Lack of experienced personnel	Inconsistent manufacturing processes	Due to lack of investigation skills	Lack of standardized procedures
Company I Mumbai, India	NA	Fear of regulatory repercussions	Inconsistent manufacturing processes	Due to perceived non-critical nature of the issue	Any other

Table 1c - Company Name and Feedback

To maintain confidentiality and follow ethical research standards, the identities of the pharmaceutical companies involved in the primary data collection have not been shared in this paper. Instead of real names, coded titles such as Company A, Company B, and so on have been used. This prevents the disclosure of sensitive business data, professional identities, and confidential operational practices.

However, for official review and academic validation, the full list of participating organizations is included in the original thesis submitted to the institution. These records are kept securely and are not released publicly to avoid any compliance concerns or possible reputational or legal impact on the organizations that participated.

Figure 3 provides a consolidated summary of responses from the pharmaceutical organizations surveyed. It highlights recurring themes associated with weaknesses in OOS investigation and documentation processes. The analysis indicates that the leading contributors to these issues include variability in manufacturing systems, limited investigation skills, and gaps in documentation training.

Figure 3: OOS Analysis Chart

RESULTS

The data collected from nine pharmaceutical organizations showed recurring gaps in how Out-of-Specification (OOS) investigations are carried out. Tables 1a, 1b, and 1c reflect the participating companies' perspectives on the questionnaire. From the feedback, several key factors contributing to OOS results were identified. Several respondents indicated that failing results were occasionally dismissed or re-tested without recording the initial values or providing adequate justification.

In many cases, investigations were incomplete because the actual root cause was not identified, and corrective steps were started prematurely.

Most companies highlighted that variation in manufacturing steps and insufficient analytical control checks were major contributors to OOS outcomes. Documentation-related weaknesses were also frequently reported, including missing rationale, incomplete entries, and poor traceability of testing records. Internal audits were seen as ineffective in identifying these deficiencies due to limited depth, checklist-based execution, or a lack of sufficiently trained auditors. Training gaps were repeatedly acknowledged as a major factor affecting the quality and consistency of investigations. Respondents commonly agreed that training aligned with regulatory expectations particularly USFDA requirements could improve compliance, investigation depth, and documentation quality. In addition, operational pressure, lack of supervision, and inadequate monitoring systems were recognized as recurring causes of repeated OOS occurrences.

Overall, the analysis reflects that OOS challenges are not only technical or testing-related

problems, but rather systemic issues linked to people competency, documentation discipline, audit capability, and process control maturity.

DISCUSSION

The results indicate that many of the challenges identified in this study mirror issues highlighted in global regulatory findings, especially those issued by the USFDA. The frequent use of re-testing and invalidation of failing results suggests that some organizations may prioritize batch release timelines over detailed scientific investigation. This approach reflects a reactive compliance mindset rather than a proactive quality-oriented culture.

The trends observed such as inconsistent manufacturing execution, undocumented decisions, and lack of structured investigation methodology show that OOS failures extend beyond laboratory operations and are connected to broader quality system gaps. Weak documentation practices and insufficient training further contribute to recurring regulatory non-compliance.

Another key observation is that employee training and competency development play a central role in improving investigation quality. Without adequate understanding of regulatory expectations, scientific reasoning, and structured problem-solving methods, OOS investigations are likely to remain superficial and repetitive.

Operational pressure and cultural factors were also highlighted as drivers for shortcuts, incomplete investigations, and poor documentation habits. This reinforces the need for leadership-driven quality culture where regulatory compliance and scientific integrity are prioritized over speed of production.

Based on the study findings, reducing OOS occurrences sustainably will require improvements in technical controls, independent and effective auditing, structured training programs, and a shift from reactive corrective actions to preventive quality management. These elements can help strengthen regulatory readiness and long-term process reliability.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that the major drivers behind Out of Specification (OOS) results are variations in manufacturing practices and insufficient control measures within production systems. In many cases, analytical checks performed in the quality control stage were unable to detect potential failures earlier in the process, allowing deviations to progress to final testing. Strengthening these foundational elements is a critical first step for minimizing OOS occurrences across the pharmaceutical sector.

Once manufacturing and testing workflows are well defined, controlled, and validated, organizations are better positioned to identify and correct procedural gaps or human errors. A reliable and reproducible process naturally reduces the likelihood of failure and ensures that product quality remains consistent with regulatory and pharmacopeial expectations.

UPCOMING OPPORTUNITIES

The study also highlights systemic weaknesses in OOS investigation protocols, including unclear procedures, limited staff training, and poor documentation discipline. These issues frequently result in incomplete investigations, making it difficult to determine the true root cause of deviations. To overcome these gaps, companies must ensure structured capacity building, allocate sufficient time for investigation activities, and reinforce scientific reasoning during failure assessment.

Every OOS case should be thoroughly recorded, reviewed, and resolved using a structured and traceable approach. In parallel, preventive systems must be strengthened by validating processes, integrating risk-based checkpoints, and implementing monitoring mechanisms designed to detect deviations early. With these improvements, organizations can transition from reactive corrections to proactive quality assurance, ultimately reducing repeat failures and improving long-term compliance.

DECLARATIONS:

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Both the author and co-author state that every ethical guideline required for conducting and publishing this research was strictly adhered to, with informed consent obtained from all participants.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

The author and coauthor declare that ethical protocols were fully observed throughout the research, with participant consent secured before initiating any data-related activities.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

This manuscript includes all relevant data collected or examined during the research, and the author is willing to provide additional raw data upon reasonable request.

COMPETING INTEREST

The authors state that there are no financial or personal relationships that could be perceived as potential conflicts of interest in connection with this work.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The completion of this research was made possible through the dedicated efforts of the author and co-authors in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting the study data.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

USFDA: United State Food and Drug Administration, **WHO TRS:** World Health Organization Technical Report Series, **OOS:** Out of Specification, **GMP:** Good Manufacturing Practices, **SOPs:** Standard Operating procedure, **FDA:** Food and Drug Administration, **CDSCO:** Central Drugs Standard Control Organization, **PIC/S-** Pharmaceutical Inspection Co-operation Scheme, **GDP:** Good Documentation Practice **CAPA:** Corrective and Preventive Actions, **MHRA:** Medicines & Healthcare products Regulatory Agency

REFERENCES

- Abrol, D., John, R., & Guha, A. (2018). Economic reforms and pharmaceutical manufacturing in India. Institute for Studies in Industrial Development (ISID).
- Abraham, B., & Kumar, R. (2020). Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd: Searching its glorious days. *South Asian Journal of Business and Management Cases*, 9(3), 359–374.
- Agarwal, V., Gupta, O., Priyadarshini, K., & Agrawal, S. A failure of regulatory diligence: A case study of Ranbaxy Laboratories Ltd.
- Ali, H., Talreja, P., & Hajela, R. (2011). Investigating an out-of-specification (OOS) result: The most challenging function in pharmaceutical industries. *Drug Invention Today*, 3(4).
- Ananth, L., Gurbani, N. K., Kumar, S., & Gujavarti, B. (2018). A retrospective study of warning letters issued by US FDA over 2015–2017. *International Journal of Drug Regulatory Affairs*, 6(2), 48–53.
- Bai, H. K., Ahearn, J. D., & Bartlett, M. G. (2021). Over-the-counter drugs: Regulatory analysis of warning letters between fiscal years 2015–2019. *Therapeutic Innovation & Regulatory Science*, 55, 426–436.
- Chatterjee, B., Dash, B., Shrestha, B., & Bhuyan, N. R. (2021). Current scenarios on regulatory landscape of Indian pharmaceutical industries.
- Chatterjee, S., Patel, H. K., & Sangirya, S. S. (2012). An analysis of the warning letters issued by the FDA to pharmaceutical manufacturers regarding misleading health outcomes claims. *Pharmacy Practice*, 10(4), 194.
- Chingale, N. D., Walunj, S. D., Kikale, M. S., Devade, O. A., & Redasani, V. (2024). Documentation essentials in the pharmaceutical industry: A regulatory perspective.
- Church, R., & Mahoney, S. (2009). Trends in FDA good manufacturing practice warning letters. *RAJ Pharma*, 20, 433–435.
- DeBell, L. E., & Chesney, D. L. (1982). The FDA inspections process. *Food, Drug, Cosmetic Law Journal*,

37(2), 244–249.

Deshpande, P., Agawane, R., Tatikola, S. C., & Vasantharaju, S. G. (2020). US FDA warning letters of CAPA violations: A review. *Applied Clinical Research, Clinical Trials and Regulatory Affairs*, 7(2), 85–92.

EMA. (2017). Guidance on Data Integrity. Available at: <https://www.ipa-india.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/p201714.pdf>

European Commission. (2020). EudraLex Volume 4 – Good Manufacturing Practice Guidelines. Available at: https://health.ec.europa.eu/medicinal-products/eudralex/eudralex-volume-4_en

FDA. (2022). FDA Form 483 – Frequently Asked Questions. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/inspections-compliance-enforcement-and-criminal-investigations/inspection-references/fda-form-483-frequently-asked-questions>

FDA. Inspection citation database. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/inspections-compliance-enforcement-and-criminal-investigations/inspection-classification-database>

FDA. Warning Letters Database. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/inspections-compliance-enforcement-and-criminal-investigations/compliance-actions-and-activities/warning-letters>

FDA. (2023). CFR Title 21 – Parts 11, 210 and 211. Available at: <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-21>

Food and Drug Administration. Drug quality sampling and testing programs. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/science-and-research-drugs/drug-quality-sampling-and-testing-programs>

Frank, M. R. (1991). FDA inspections: A practical corporate response. *Food Drug Cosmetic Law Journal*, 46, 71.

Gowtham, V., Ashok, K., Gupta, N., Gangadharappa, H., Aswani, N., & Shivakumar, H. (2011). Documentation in obtaining US FDA approval for a tablet manufacturing facility. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*, 4(11), 3989–3991.

Hile, J. P. (1974). Food and drug administration inspections: A new approach. *Food Drug Cosmetic Law Journal*, 29, 101.

Hoinowski, A. M., Motola, S., Davis, R. J., & McArdle, J. V. (2002). Investigation of out-of-specification results. *Pharmaceutical Technology*, 26(1), 40–51.

Indian FDA Guidance. (2022). Investigating Out-of-Specification (OOS) Test Results for Pharmaceutical Production. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/media/158416/download>

Jain, S. K., & Jain, R. K. (2017). Investigations and CAPA: Quality system for continual improvement in pharmaceutical industry. *International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2, 47–54.

Jain, S. K., & Jain, R. K. (2018). Review of FDA warning letters to pharmaceuticals: Cause and effect analysis. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 11(7), 3219–3226.

Jain, S. K., & Jain, R. K. (2020). Avoiding warning letters in pharmaceutical industry: A qualitative study in the Indian context. *The Pharma Innovation*, 9(6), 18–24.

Kamal, R., Diksha, Paul, P., & Awasthi, A. (2024). Steering through regulatory currents: The journey of India's pharma industry with the USFDA. *Applied Drug Research, Clinical Trials and Regulatory Affairs*, 10(1).

Kiernan, R. D. (1988). Factory inspection: Responding to an issued FDA Form 483. *Food Drug Cosmetic Law Journal*, 43, 699.

Kolekar, P. D., & Bhagwat, A. M. (2021). Good documentation practices: A need of pharmaceutical industry.

Kumar, K. A., & Gupta, N. V. (2015). Handling of out-of-specification results. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance*, 6(2), 38–44.

Kuselman, I., et al. (2010-2013). (Multiple publications consolidated.)

McDowall, R. (2020). Are you invalidating out-of-specification results into compliance?

Neves, E. O., de Sales, P. M., & Silveira, D. (2020). Pharmacopeial specifications and analytical data from post-marketing programs. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 178, 112935.

Patel, A. B., et al. (2022). A retrospective study of warning letters issued by US FDA 2019-2021. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 12(4), 295–301.

Patel, D. S. (2012). FDA warning letter analysis: A tool for GMP compliance. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 3(12), 4592.

Patel, D. P., Kanaki, N., Movaliya, V., & Zaveri, M. (2023). Review on inspectional observation and warning letters. *International Journal of Drug Regulatory Affairs*, 11(2), 64–67.

Pazhayatil, A. B., Sayeed, N., & Ingram, M. (2019). Lessons from FDA 483s and inspection data. *Pharmaceutical Technology*, 43(10).

Poska, R., & Graham, B. (2009). FDA 483 responses—Suggestions for industry. *Journal of Validation Technology*, 15(2), 57.

Rathore, A. S., Li, Y., Chhabra, H., & Lohiya, A. (2023). FDA warning letters: Retrospective analysis 2010–2020. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Innovation*, 18(2), 665–674.

Ravi, G., Gupta, N. V., Raghunandan, H. V., & Shashikanth, D. (2013). FDA guidelines for OOS. *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, 5(3), 943–948.

Saini, C., Miglani, A., Musyuni, P., & Aggarwal, G. (2022). Review of form 483s and warning letters. *Journal*

of Generic Medicines, 18(1), 32–41.

Shah, N. K. (2020). Financial statement analysis of pharmaceutical companies. *GAP Interdisciplinarity*, 3(6), 321–331.

Shashikant, G. S., Chhabra, G., & Nayan, G. (2018). Handling market complaints and recalls: Review of FDA-483. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*, 6(3), 55–59.

Swartz, M., & Krull, I. (2004). Investigating out-of-specification results. *LCGC North America*, 22(2), 132–137.

Tripathy, S., Pandey, P., Mohanty, S., Murthy, P. N., & Guruswamy, S. (2017). Audit and compliance: Bird's eye on current Indian pharma. *Applied Clinical Research, Clinical Trials and Regulatory Affairs*, 4(2), 114–119.

Ul Alam, A. M. (2024). Analyzing FDA Form 483 data of 2023. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Sciences*, 12(1), 3–7.

Unger, B. (2014). An analysis of FDA FY2016 drug GMP warning letters. *Pharmaceutical Online*. Available at: <https://www.pharmaceuticalonline.com/doc/an-analysisof-fda-fy-drug-gmp-warning-letters-0001>

United States Pharmacopeia. (2020). USP <1010>: Outlier testing. Available at: http://ftp.uspbpep.com/v29240/usp29nf24s0_c1010.html

World Health Organization. (2017). WHO global surveillance and monitoring system for substandard and falsified medical products. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241513425>

World Health Organization. (2018). WHO TRS 986 Annex 2: Good manufacturing practices for pharmaceutical products. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/trs986-annex2>

World Health Organization. (2020). WHO TRS 1033 Annex 4: Guideline on data integrity. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/annex-4-trs-1033>

Winchell, T. (2011). FDA warning letter: Avoidance and advice. *The Quality Assurance Journal*, 14(3–4), 76–79.